

Planting density and submergence level were significantly but negatively correlated with and substantially affected weed density. Weed density decreased from 84 to 10 weeds/m² when planting density was increased from 15 to 42 hills/m² (Fig. 1). Increasing submergence level from 0.0 to 6.5 cm reduced weed density from 94 to 20 weeds/m² (Fig. 2). □

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgement to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.

2. Relationship between submergence and weed density.

Soil and crop management

Influence of seed rate and timing of fertilizer application on wet seeded rice yield

Prasert-Songmuang, Nikool Rangwichon, and Wittaya Seetanun, Rice Fertilization Research Branch, Soil Science Division, Bangkok, and Suphan Buri Rice Experiment Station (SBRES), Suphan Buri, Thailand

Transplanted rice area in the central plain of Thailand is diminishing and wet seeded rice area is increasing, especially in irrigated systems. An experiment to determine optimum seed rate and timing of fertilizer application for wet seeded rice was

conducted at SBRES during the 1981 dry season.

conducted at SBRES during the 1981 dry season.

Soil at the experimental site was Nakhon Pathom clay, with pH 5.1, 2.97% organic matter, and cation exchange capacity 22 meq/100 g soil. Pregerminated seeds were sown at 62, 94, and 125 kg/ha. Ammonium phosphate (16-20-0) at 219 kg/ha was applied at different times after sowing and 200 kg ammonium sulfate (21% N)/ha was applied at panicle initiation.

Results showed that 62 kg seed/ha was optimum and suggested that chemical fertilizer can be applied up to 30 days after sowing (see table). □

Effect on ratoon rice of cutting height and time of nitrogen application on the main crop

Md. Abdul Quddus, scientific officer, Division of Rice Cropping Systems, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute; and J. W. Pendleton, Multiple Cropping Department IRRI

Ratoon rice may increase production where limited rainfall and soil moisture reduce cropping intensity. We studied the effect of main-crop management practices on the performance of ratoon rice at the IRRI farm July 1980 to January 1981.

Nitrogen was applied on breeding line IR9784-2-3-2 as described in Table 1. The main crop was harvested by cutting 5 cm and 15 cm above soil surface and by ani-ani (a method where only the panicles are cut). Plants were cut to 15 cm 7 days after the ani-ani harvest. Two days after harvest 40 kg N/ha was applied to all plots. To encourage tiller growth, fields were flooded with 2-3 cm water 2-3 days after harvest. Water depth was gradually increased to 5-7 cm and maintained at that level until grain ripened.

Nitrogen application at different main-crop plant growth stages did not affect grain yield or other plant characters of the main crop (Table 1). Yield was not influenced by cutting height, but a 5-cm cutting height produced significantly

Effect of seed rate and time of fertilizer application on grain yield of RD7 rice (av of 4 replications). Suphan Buri Rice Experiment Station, 1981 dry season.

Time of fertilizer application ^a	Grain yield (t/ha) at seed rate of			Mean yield ^b (t/ha)
	62 kg/ha	94 kg/ha	125 kg/ha	
Incorporated BS	5.5	4.9	5.2	5.2a
10 DS	5.5	5.1	4.9	5.2a
20 DS	5.5	4.8	5.2	5.2a
30 DS	5.5	5.1	4.9	5.2a
40 DS	5.1	4.6	4.8	4.8 b
Mean	5.4	4.9	5.0	
				F value ^c
Seed rate (R)				8.30*
CV (a)	8.7%			
Time of fertilizer application (T)				4.02**
R × T				< 1 ^{ns}
CV (b)	5.5%			

^aBS = before sowing, DS = days after sowing. ^bMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different among themselves. ^c*Significant at 5% level; **significant at 1% level. ns = non-significant. LSD 0.05 for 2 seed rate means = 0.1 t/ha.

Table 1. Grain yield and other plant characters of the main crop of IR9784-2-3-2 as affected by N application. IRRI, 1980 wet season.

Basal	Treatment (kg N/ha)				Plant characters ^a					
	Panicle initiation	Early milk stage	Late milk stage	7 days before harvest	Grain yield (t/ha)	Tillers (no./m ²)	Panicles (no./hill)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	100-grain weight (g)	
60	30	0	0	0	3.6	425	16	49	2.2	
30	30	30	0	0	3.5	415	15	46	2.2	
30	30	0	30	0	3.7	448	16	43	2.1	
30	30	0	0	30	3.6	439	15	48	2.1	

^aAv of 4 replications. Analysis of variance showed no difference between treatments at 5% probability level.

higher percentage of missing hills than harvesting at 15 cm or by ani-ani (Table 2). At 5 cm, panicles per hill or per unit area were less than for other treatments. Difference in grain yields was not statistically significant. Plants cut at 5 cm height had more healthy ratoon tillers, heavier grains, and more even maturity than other treatments. They matured in 74 days versus 65 days for 15 cm and 69 days for ani-ani. □

Table 2. Grain yield and other plant characters of a ratoon crop of IR9784-2-3-2 as affected by cutting height of main crop. IRRI, July 1980-January 1981.

Cutting height (cm)	Plant character ^a					
	Grain yield (t/ha)	Productive tillers (no./m ²)	Panicles (no./hill)	Missing hills (%)	Field duration (days)	100-grain weight (%)
5	0.6a	237 b	10 b	7.0a	74a	2.2a
15	0.5a	323a	13a	5.2 b	65 c	2.1 b
ani-ani fb 15 cm	0.6a	316a	13a	3.8 b	69 b	2.2a

^aAv of 4 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. Also an average of all N treatments. fb = followed by.

Azolla application and rice crop response in Tamil Nadu

S. Kannaiyan, M. Thangaraju, G. Alagirisami, J. Venkatakishnan, S. Kanagaraj, and G. Oblisami, Agricultural Microbiology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641 003, Tamil Nadu, India

Azolla is a water fern that fixes nitrogen (N) in association with N-fixing blue-green alga *Anabaena azollae*. Four field

experiments were conducted during 1981-82 samba (Oct-Feb). IR20 (at Coimbatore), Bhavani (Ahyarnagar), IR20 (Tirurkuppam), and Ponni (Ambasamudrum) were evaluated using treatments described in the table.

Grain yield for all treatments was higher than for the untreated control. Plots treated with 30 kg N/ha and 30 kg N/ha as azolla at 40 × 10 cm spacing had maximum grain yield followed by plots treated with 60 kg N/ha at 20 × 20 cm spacing at

Aliyarnagar center (see table). A similar trend was observed at Ambasamudrum center, but at Tirurkuppam center plots treated with 60 kg N/ha at 30 × 20 cm spacing had maximum grain yield. At Coimbatore, maximum grain yield was for plots with azolla incorporation as green manure before planting and azolla grown twice as dual crop until heading. Results clearly show the positive influence of azolla inoculation in increasing grain yield. □

Rice crop response to azolla, Tamil Nadu, 1982.

Treatments ^a	Yield (t/ha)							
	Coimbatore		Ambasamudrum		Aliyarnagar		Tirurkuppam	
	IR20	% increase	Ponni	% increase	Bhavani	% increase	IR20	% increase
Uninoculated control, 20 × 20 cm	2.7	—	3.2	—	1.9	—	1.9	—
60 kg N/ha, 20 × 20 cm	4.3	59	3.9	21	2.9	54	2.9	52
60 kg N/ha, 40 × 10 cm	4.1	52	3.9	21	2.7	43	2.7	44
30 kg N/ha by azolla + 30 kg N/ha, 20 × 20 cm	4.3	58	3.8	18	2.7	45	2.4	25
30 kg N/ha by azolla + 30 kg N/ha, 40 × 10 cm	4.2	53	4.0	23	2.9	55	2.4	29
Azolla GM + azolla DC, 20 × 20 cm	4.4	64	3.7	14	2.6	38	2.6	36
Azolla GM + azolla DC, 40 × 10 cm	4.1	51	3.5	9	2.4	27	2.4	29
Azolla DC, 40 × 10 cm	4.1	50	3.4	3	2.5	32	2.5	35

C.D. = 497

C.D. = 387

C.D. = 910

C.D. = 210

^aGM = green manure, DC = dual crop. N was applied as 3 splits. *Azolla pinnata* was inoculated at 300 g/m² on the 7th day after planting.